

Supporting Information

Sol-gel thin films for the protection of ancient glass artefacts: a performance comparison between inorganic and hybrid silica compositions

Stefano Centenaro^{a,b}, E. Cattaruzza^b, A. Glisenti^c, L. Puppulin^b, Giulia Franceschin^{a,} and Arianna Traviglia^{a,*}*

This document includes

Supporting text

Supporting figures S1 to S9

Details on SR-IR and ATR-IR analysis. The SR-IR spectrum of a silica soda lime slide in the whole range of acquisition is reported in Figure S1. In the low wavenumber region, from 1250 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} , there are two dominant peaks at $\approx 1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\approx 466\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a smaller peak at $\approx 763\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The peak at approximately 1060 cm^{-1} is due to the stretching motion of the Si-O-Si bond in the silicate network, as demonstrated by theoretical calculations conducted by Bell ^[1]. These are referred to as bridging oxygen (BO) atoms because they connect neighbouring silicon atoms in the silicate network ^[2]. Later, Galeener suggested that the dominant peak at approximately 1060 cm^{-1} is associated to the asymmetric Si-O-Si stretch, the weak band at $\approx 765\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to the symmetric Si-O-Si stretch, and the $\approx 466\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band arises from the rocking motion of Si-O-Si ^[3]. These assignments have been adopted in IR spectroscopy studies ever since ^[4-6].

The small shoulder observed at approximately 950 cm^{-1} has been suggested to be associated with the stretching vibration of Si-OH or Si-O⁻ species ^[7]. These species are known as non-bridging oxygen (NBO) atoms because they interrupt the network connectivity ^[8]. Historically, the 950 cm^{-1} band was attributed to the vibration of Si-O of NBOs associated with modifier ions ^[9]. Recently, molecular dynamics simulations showed that the 950 cm^{-1} shoulder could be the vibrations of the Si-O-Si network with a red-shift from the $\approx 1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$ position due to the network disruption caused by NBOs rather than being a specific vibration of NBOs only ^[10].

The shoulder observed at approximately 1180 cm^{-1} was attributed to the longitudinal optic (LO) mode of the network vibrations due to the longitudinal-transverse (LO-TO) splittings ^[11]. In crystals, these splittings arise as a result of long-range Coulomb forces which are a consequence of the internal electric field created by the motions of the ions during the vibrations ^[12]. Leeuw and Thorpe demonstrated through numerical calculations the existence of TO-LO splittings also in random networks, such as that of glasses ^[13]. However, this interpretation has recently been questioned, suggesting that the observed effects may instead be attributed to optical phenomena of the reflection process resulting from off-normal incidence angles ^[14].

Figure S1. SR-IR spectrum of silica soda lime glass slide (on the left) and magnification of the silica fingerprint region (on the right).

The nearly zero reflectance observed at approximately 1270 cm^{-1} in Figure S1 is due to the similarity in refractive indices between the silica soda lime glass slide and air, as illustrated in Figure S2.

Figure S2. Real part (n) of the refractive index for a soda lime glass on the left (black line); imaginary part (k) of the refractive index for a soda lime glass plotted from data reported on ^[15] on the right (red line).

In the high wavenumber region, bands at approximately 2200 cm^{-1} , 2900 cm^{-1} , and 3500 cm^{-1} arise due to the contribution from the backside reflection which can lead to artifacts in the spectrum. The penetration depth d_p of SR-IR is defined as in Equation (S1) ^[16]:

$$d_p = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi k} \quad (\text{S1})$$

Figure S3 shows that penetration depth varies from approximately $0.6\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ at the asymmetric Si-O-Si stretch band ($\approx 1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$) to $3.4\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ at the symmetric Si-O-Si stretch band ($\approx 765\text{ cm}^{-1}$), to $1.3\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ at the Si-O-Si rocking motion band ($\approx 466\text{ cm}^{-1}$). If the glass sample thickness is, like in our case, $\approx 1\text{ mm}$, then the wavenumber region higher than $\approx 2200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be reflected from the backside of the glass sample. Therefore, the peak at approximately 2200 cm^{-1} is an artifact due to the non-zero reflection contribution of the glass backside. These calculations were experimentally validated through a control experiment in which the backside of the 1.2 mm thick glass slide was mechanically roughened. As shown in Figure S3, this process successfully suppressed the reflection contribution from the backside.

Figure S3. SR-IR penetration depth, $d_{p,\text{SR-IR}}$, inside silica soda lime glass calculated with $k(\lambda)$ shown in Fig. 2.12, experimentally obtained SR-IR spectra of soda lime glass with different backside reflection conditions (on the right).

Therefore, due to the influence of the backside reflection, from now on we will consider only the part of the SR-IR spectrum in the range 400 cm^{-1} to 1300 cm^{-1} .

Considering the sol-gel depositions, the differences in the reflectance curves between the coatings and the bare glass surface affect the position of the dominant peak (main maximum), and the generation of a second (satellite) maximum with an intermediate minimum.

The observed pattern can be attributed to the difference of numerical values between the optical constants (n and k) of the sol-gel film and the substrate^[16]. As an approximation, assuming the optical constants of bulk SiO₂ (Figure S4) for the inorganic sol-gel thin films, we observed that the main peaks in the n and k spectra, at ≈ 1042 cm⁻¹ and ≈ 1100 cm⁻¹ respectively, are blue shifted with respect to the main peaks in the n and k spectra for silica soda lime glass, which occur at ≈ 910 cm⁻¹ and ≈ 1020 cm⁻¹ respectively. This trend is also observed in the experimental data, which show that the main maxima in the case of the sol-gel coatings are shifted towards higher wavelengths compared to the silica soda lime glass slide. This behaviour validates the hypothesis that the coating has a “silica-like” structure. Considering the satellite band, it closely resembles bands typically attributed to SiOH and Si-O⁻ modifier bonds in the spectra of leached glasses^[17].

Figure S4. Real part (n) of the refractive index for fused quartz glass on the left (black line); imaginary part (k) of the refractive index for fused quartz glass plotted from data reported on^[18] on the right (red line).

Figure S5 displays the ATR-IR spectrum of a silica soda lime glass slide in the whole range of acquisition. The position of the two dominant Si-O-Si peaks differ significantly from the absorption band shown in the $k(\lambda)$ spectrum (Figure S2). This red shift is attributed to the strong variation in the real (n) and imaginary (k) part of the refractive index in the 900 cm⁻¹ - 1200 cm⁻¹ and in the 350 cm⁻¹ - 500 cm⁻¹ wavelength region (Figure S2), which leads to the distortion in both the shape and position of the peak in the ATR-IR spectrum^[19].

Therefore, by comparing the SR-IR and ATR-IR spectra, the two dominant peaks at ≈ 1060 cm⁻¹ and ≈ 466 cm⁻¹ in SR-IR are both strongly red shifted to ≈ 912 cm⁻¹ and ≈ 385 cm⁻¹ respectively. Conversely, the weak band at ≈ 765 cm⁻¹ in SR-IR falls almost at the same wavelength in the ATR-IR spectrum due to the minimal variation in n and k within the 650 cm⁻¹ to 850 cm⁻¹ wavelength region (Figure S2). Considering the penetration depth, in ATR-IR the evanescent wave exhibits an exponential decay as a function of the distance from the surface within the sample. Therefore, the penetration depth is defined as the distance at which the electric field intensity within the sample falls to 37% of its initial value at the surface. In the case of a media with a $k \approx 0$, the d_p is calculated as shown in Equation (S2)^[20]:

$$d_p = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi n_c \sqrt{\sin^2 \theta - \left(\frac{n_s}{n_c}\right)^2}} \quad (\text{S2})$$

where λ is the wavelength of the IR beam, θ is the incident angle, n_c is the real part of the refractive index of the internal reflection crystal and n_s is the real part of the refractive index of the sample. This approximation is valid in the wavenumber region of interest (4000 cm^{-1} - 500 cm^{-1}) for the diamond crystal [21]. However, for silica soda lime glass, as shown in Figure S2, this approximation is only valid in the high wavenumber region, from 4000 cm^{-1} to 1250 cm^{-1} , while in the low wavenumber region, from 1250 cm^{-1} to 250 cm^{-1} , $k \gg 0$. Therefore, in Eq 2.7, the real part of the refractive index of the sample n_s should be substituted with the complex refractive index of the sample n'_s defined as in Equation (S3):

$$n'_s = n_s + ik_s \quad (\text{S3})$$

where k_s is the imaginary part of the refractive index of the sample. Thus, Equation (S2) becomes Equation (S4):

$$d_p = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi n_c \sqrt{\sin^2 \theta - \left(\frac{n'_s}{n_c}\right)^2}} \quad (\text{S4})$$

Figure S5 illustrates the variation in penetration depth across the 350 cm^{-1} - 3850 cm^{-1} region. The most significant difference in penetration depth with respect to SR-IR is registered for wavenumbers higher than 1200 cm^{-1} . In this region, the penetration depth of ATR-IR is lower by 1 to 4 orders of magnitude compared to SR-IR (Figure S3).

Figure S5. ATR-IR spectrum of silica soda lime glass slide (on the left); ATR-IR penetration depth, $d_{p,ATR}$ of silica soda lime glass calculated with $n(\lambda)$ and $k(\lambda)$ shown in Fig. 2.12 (on the right).

Considering the sol-gel depositions, similarly to the SR-IR, it was assumed that the inorganic sol-gel thin films exhibit properties similar to SiO_2 . The calculated ATR-IR penetration depth (Figure S6) shows that the influence of the substrate dominates the spectral signal.

Figure S6. Penetration depth $d_{p,ATR}$ of quartz glass calculated with $n(\lambda)$ and $k(\lambda)$ shown in Figure S4.

Determination of reflected and transmitted light fraction. The fraction of reflected and transmitted light of glass in the visible range (400-700 nm) can be determined using the Fresnel equations [22]. In case the angle of incidence is perpendicular to the glass surface, the fraction of reflected light is given by the following Equation (S5) [23]:

$$R = \frac{(n_0 - n_g)^2}{(n_0 + n_g)^2} \quad (\text{S5})$$

where R is the specular reflectance, n_0 being the refractive index of the medium the light is coming from (e.g., air with $n \approx 1$) and n_G being the refractive index of the glass. Since the light passing through glass is not only reflected on the front surface, but also on the back, the overall reflectance through a glass slide (R_t) is expressed as Equation (6) [24]:

$$R_t = \frac{2R}{(1+R)} \quad (\text{S6})$$

According to these formulas, about 8% of the light is reflected from soda-lime glass slides, assuming perpendicular incidence angle and no absorption and scattering.

Details on X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy analysis of the samples after ageing.

Having a superficial sampling depth (≈ 10 nm), XPS analysis enabled investigation of the top layers of the glass surface. It is known that when performing XPS analysis the presence of a thin layer of carbon-based material is quite always detected on the surface of air-exposed samples [25]. This adventitious carbon contamination, usually present at the surface in atomic concentrations around 10-15%, does not represent the actual composition of the glass but rather an extraneous layer that skews the quantitative analysis. Therefore, in Table 3 we choose to report compositions by considering only the constitutive elements in the glass.

Figure S7. Photographs of the glass samples SGT (a), SGTM (b), and SGTO (c) after accelerated ageing.

Figure S8. AFM morphological images of the inorganic SG122M coating as deposited (on the left) and of the bare glass surface (on the right); note the different colour scale, which highlights a decrease in surface roughness on the coated sample. Root mean square roughness values, R_q , are reported in the images.

Figure S9. AFM morphological images of the SG122M coating as deposited (on the left) and of the SG122M coating after artificial ageing (on the right); note the different colour scale. Root mean square roughness values, R_q , are also reported.

References

- [1] R. J. Bell, P. Dean, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.* **1970**, *50*, 55.
- [2] J. Serra, P. González, S. Liste, C. Serra, S. Chiussi, B. León, M. Pérez-Amor, H. O. Ylänen, M. Hupa, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **2003**, *332*, 20.
- [3] F. L. Galeener, *Phys. Rev. B* **1979**, *19*, 4292.
- [4] P. McMillan, *American Mineralogist* **1984**, *69*, 622.
- [5] F. Gervais, A. Blin, D. Massiot, J. P. Coutures, M. H. Chopinet, F. Naudin, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **1987**, *89*, 384.
- [6] W. R. Taylor, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Earth Planet Sci.)* **1990**, *99*, 99.
- [7] R. M. Almeida, T. A. Guiton, C. G. Pantano, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **1990**, *121*, 193.
- [8] J. Serra, P. González, S. Liste, S. Chiussi, B. León, M. Pérez-Amor, H. O. Ylänen, M. Hupa, *J Mater Sci Mater Med* **2002**, *13*, 1221.
- [9] D. M. Sanders, W. B. Person, L. L. Hench, *Appl. Spectrosc., AS* **1974**, *28*, 247.
- [10] H. Liu, S. H. Hahn, M. Ren, M. Thiruvillamalai, T. M. Gross, J. Du, A. C. T. van Duin, S. H. Kim, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* **2020**, *103*, 3575.
- [11] R. M. Almeida, *Phys. Rev. B* **1992**, *45*, 161.
- [12] M. F. Thorpe, S. W. de Leeuw, *Phys. Rev. B* **1986**, *33*, 8490.
- [13] S. W. de Leeuw, M. F. Thorpe, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1985**, *55*, 2879.
- [14] H. Liu, H. Kaya, Y.-T. Lin, A. Ogrinc, S. H. Kim, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* **2022**, *105*, 2355.
- [15] M. Rubin, *Solar Energy Materials* **1985**, *12*, 275.
- [16] F. Geotti-Bianchini, L. De Riu, G. Gagliardi, M. Guglielmi, C. G. Pantano, *Glastechnische Berichte* **1991**, *64*, 205.
- [17] F. Geotti-Bianchini, M. Preo, M. Guglielmi, C. G. Pantano, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **2003**, *321*, 110.
- [18] J. Kischkat, S. Peters, B. Gruska, M. Semtsiv, M. Chashnikova, M. Klinkmüller, O. Fedosenko, S. Machulik, A. Aleksandrova, G. Monastyrskyi, Y. Flores, W. T. Masselink, *Appl. Opt., AO* **2012**, *51*, 6789.
- [19] S. Amma, J. Luo, C. G. Pantano, S. H. Kim, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **2015**, *428*, 189.
- [20] S. Amma, S. H. Kim, C. G. Pantano, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* **2016**, *99*, 128.

- [21] D. F. Edwards, H. R. Philipp, in *Handbook of Optical Constants of Solids* (Ed.: E. D. Palik), Academic Press, Burlington, **1997**, pp. 665–673.
- [22] R. Persson, in *Flat Glass Technology* (Ed.: R. Persson), Springer US, Boston, MA, **1969**, pp. 39–52.
- [23] E. Hecht, A. Zajac, *Optics*, Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, Boston, MA, **1974**.
- [24] V. Augugliaro, V. Loddo, M. Pagliaro, G. Palmisano, L. Palmisano, *Clean by Light Irradiation*, The Royal Society Of Chemistry, **2010**.
- [25] L. H. Grey, H.-Y. Nie, M. C. Biesinger, *Applied Surface Science* **2024**, 653, 159319.